

Deliverable D7.1

Driver validation report of Year 1 EOSC-ENTRUST architectural blueprint including gap analysis

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AAAI	Authentication Authorisation Auditing/Accounting Infrastructure
BAM	Binary Alignment Map
crMDR	clinical research Metadata Repository
D	Deliverable
DAAMS	Data Access Application Management System, the system to request access to data under EHDS Regulation
DAC	Data Access Committee
EGA	European Genome-Phenome Archive
EHDS	European Health Data Space
eID	Electronic Identification (across Europe)
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICTRP	International Clinical Trials Registry Platform
IDAN	International Data Access Network
IG	Information Governance
IPD	Individual Participant Data
LLM	Large Language Model
MoSCoW	M - Must have; S - Should have; C - Could have; W - Won't have
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
PI	Principal Investigator
RDI	Research, Development and Innovation
SATRE	Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments
SDC	Statistical Disclosure Control
SIESTA	Secure Interactive Environments for SensiTive data Analytics
SPE	Secure Processing Environment that fulfills the requirements of EHDS

SSO	Single Sign On
TRE	Trusted Research Environment
UKDS	UK Data Service
WHO	World Health Organisation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability between TREs by development of a common blueprint (hereafter the ENTRUST Blueprint) for federated data access and analysis. The project is supported by four driver projects (hereafter Drivers), i.e. use cases which are prototypic for federated, multinational use of TREs in research practice across scientific domains and user communities:

- Federated Human Genomics as a catalyst for European TRE provision (EMBL, CRG, BSC)
- Common standards to enable trans-national sharing of administrative and social science data (CESSDA, GESIS, UKDS, TARKI)
- Enabling the re-use of clinical trials data for research purposes across Europe (ECRIN, UiO, HDR UK, UNIVDUN)
- Public-Private interactions between TRE in health and environmental data (Turku UAS, CSC, Sigma2)

The Drivers (united in WP7) (I) inform the development of and validate the blueprint and (II) provide user input to the provider forum by stating their requirements for a TRE.

The present deliverable report provides:

- An updated and refined set of requirements from the four Drivers
- Concrete Driver use cases that the Blueprint should support
- A generic user journey that the Blueprint should support, based on Drivers' user journeys and a gap analysis
- A gap analysis between the Driver requirements and the first version of the Blueprint

How does the work summarized in this deliverable contribute to the overall project objectives?

- The Driver requirements and the gap analysis between the Driver requirements and the Blueprint lead to recommendations for version 2 of the Blueprint.
- The generic user journey from the perspective of both data users and data holders provides a basis for identifying gaps in existing TRE services available within the Provider Forum.
- The process of gathering and mapping requirements for the Drivers provides the foundation for a requirement gathering framework targeted to anyone considering building a TRE.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	No
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	Yes
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	No
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	No
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	No
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	Yes
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	No

framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes ¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)	No
	5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 3 National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes	1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
	2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).	No
	3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No
Objective 4 The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.	1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No
	2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).	No
	3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)	Yes

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

3. Methods

3.1 Deliverable scope

The D7.1 Deliverable aims to validate the year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework² (ENTRUST Blueprint) against the baseline requirements set by the four Drivers.

The baseline requirements for the four Drivers were initially reported in the internal M7.1 milestone report³, delivered by the Drivers (WP7) in August 2024. The first version of the ENTRUST Blueprint was delivered as D13.4 by the architecture work package (WP13) in December 2024. The present deliverable report presents refined requirements from the four Drivers, prototypic use cases, the usage patterns found in the Drivers, Gaps between the Driver requirements and the ENTRUST Blueprint and an updated generic user journey that should be supported by the ENTRUST Blueprint.

The Drivers will continue to revise and harmonize their requirements in 2025, taking into account the needs of WP13 (Architecture) and WP16 (AAAI). This will result in a complete set of Driver requirements which can inform the final versions of the ENTRUST Blueprint (WP13/14), the AAAI system (WP16/17), and the Deployable demonstrator (WP19/20). The Drivers will collaborate closely with WP10 (Providers) to support the development of a common requirements management framework for the EOSC-ENTRUST project.

3.2 Methodology

3.2.1 Design thinking approach

The four Drivers provide a user-centric perspective for validating and implementing the ENTRUST Blueprint. The validation of the year 1 version of the Blueprint, detailed in the current deliverable report, builds on the Drivers' baseline requirements from the M7.1 milestone report.

The validation process considers the perspectives of both data users and data holders, using an iterative, design thinking approach. Key steps include refining the individual Driver

² Sætrum, P., Lehvälaiho, H., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., & Hesam, A. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14362388>

³ Anne van der Kant, Jan-Willem Boiten, Milestone report M7.1 Initial Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers [unpublished].

requirements, applying the MoSCoW⁴ method, identifying users, mapping their journeys, identifying gaps, and defining typical use cases to illustrate user patterns. A number of these steps were taken in online meetings within the Drivers WP as well as with other WPs. Gap analyses on the ENTRUST Blueprint and the proposed generic user journey were performed by the Drivers in collaboration with WP13 (Architecture), WP10 (Providers), WP16 (AAAI) and WP19 (Deployable Demonstrator) during the EOSC-ENTRUST *Blueprint Validation Workshop*, held as a hybrid meeting in Utrecht, January 21-22, 2025. The steps towards validating the ENTRUST Blueprint are further illustrated in the following sections.

Figure 1: Process followed to iteratively refine Drivers' requirements to validate and inform the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint.

3.2.2 User and user journey and usage pattern mapping

Users

Key users and individual user journeys for each Driver were described in the M7.1 milestone report. The users reported in Table 2 of the M7.1 milestone report were augmented with additional user profiles that were identified in the Blueprint validation workshop included in the *Results* section (Table 1).

⁴ The MoSCoW method is a prioritisation technique used to categorise and prioritise project requirements or features into four distinct categories: M - Must have: Absolutely critical requirements that are essential for project success; S - Should have: Important features that are not time-sensitive but still significant; C - Could have: Desirable but non-critical features that can be added if time permits; W - Won't have: Features explicitly excluded from the current project scope. The method helps to make informed decisions about resource allocation, focus on delivering critical elements first, and prevent scope deviation.

User journeys

The mapping of the user journeys of the four Drivers resulted in a generic user journey (Figure 2), which was discussed at the First EOSC-ENTRUST Evaluation & Adoption workshop in Helsinki, September 2024⁵. Based on the feedback from that workshop a new version was presented to the Drivers as the basis for a gap analysis performed at the Blueprint Validation Workshop in January 2025 and described in the present report. An updated version of the generic user journey can be found in the *Results* section, where the identified gaps have been addressed.

Figure 2: Generic user journey that was used as a basis for the gap analysis. Three roles have been distinguished, where each roles' actions are shown in a distinct color: *Data user*: orange, *TRE*: blue, *Data holder*: green.

Usage patterns

The year-one version of the ENTRUST Blueprint² included an initial analysis of the data usage patterns of the four Drivers. Figure 2 (adapted from the Blueprint) illustrates the different usage patterns. Four different data patterns may be distinguished for a project's required data, each posing specific challenges when jointly analyzing the data, including data sharing and/or individual record linking. Both *data subjects* and *attributes* of data subjects (for example, a blood pressure measurement) might be spread over multiple TREs. In this report, the four Drivers report their usage patterns in order to inventorize the most pressing data sharing challenges.

⁵ Kirschenmann, S., Kallberg, M., Repo, S., Sætrom, P., Azab, A., Balčirák, P., Baxter, R., Kulseth Dahl, P., Laine, H., Maccallum, P., Stansberg, C., Soiland-Reyes, S., & van der Kant, A. (2024). First EOSC-ENTRUST Evaluation and Adoption Workshop. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13860340>

Figure 3: Data distribution. Different types of individual-level sensitive data (columns; distinct colours represent distinct datasets) are split between different geographically and/or governance-wise distinct regions (rows; one row represents one individual). Analyses can use a single dataset (Q0), the same attributes from different individuals residing in multiple regions (Q1), different attributes from the same individuals (Q2), or multiple attributes from the same individuals, which are residing in multiple regions (Q3). Figure adapted from EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework².

Prototypic use case

The TRE usage patterns across the domains covered in each of the Drivers may look similar. Nevertheless, there are differences that can be uncovered by looking into the specifics of the TRE usage in each of the Drivers. In order to make this tangible, each of the Drivers has selected one or two prototypic use cases highlighting 1) the purpose of the TRE usage; 2) showing the typical TRE users; 3) illustrating the user journey throughout the Driver usage of a TRE. The prototypic use cases also served as a demonstrator to adequately map Drivers' needs to the ENTRUST Blueprint for the gap analysis.

3.2.3 Requirements gathering and refinement

Initial Driver requirements were gathered in a common requirements matrix included with the M7.1 milestone report. Leading up to the present deliverable, these requirements have been refined by the Drivers, aiming to deliver:

- Requirements formulated on the functional level, without descriptions of specific implementation choices;
- A complete overview of relevance of each requirement to each Driver, using the MoSCoW classification;

- Requirements mapped to the SATRE⁶ (*Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments*) framework;
- Requirements that clearly state the interoperability needs of the Drivers on a functional level, as a starting point for discussion on how a federation⁷ might address these needs.

The resulting set of Driver requirements can be found in Appendix 2.

The SATRE framework, widely recognised in the UK, has served as a key reference in this process. This framework defines the capabilities expected from a TRE, categorised into mandatory and optional requirements. We used this framework as a foundation in our approach to develop the initial set of requirements.

3.2.4 Validation of the year 1 version of the ENTRUST Blueprint

Validation of the year-one version of the ENTRUST Blueprint was performed through a gap analysis between the Drivers' requirements and the ENTRUST Blueprint. This gap analysis expands upon the gap analysis between the DARE-UK Blueprint and the Driver requirements that was performed for the Blueprint deliverable. The Drivers collaborated with WP13 (Architecture), WP16 (AAAI), WP19 (Workflow Processing) and WP10 (Providers) on the gap analysis during the *Blueprint Validation Workshop*. To lay the foundation for this gap analysis, the workshop kicked-off with introductory presentations about the Blueprint by WP13 and the proposed requirements for AAAI by WP16.

Thereafter, the four Drivers worked on the gap analysis for their Driver in breakouts, supported by representatives from WP10, WP13, WP16, and WP19. The four Drivers used the generic user journey, together with the individual Driver's prototypic use case(s), as a basis to further map Driver requirements to the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and identify gaps. The gaps identified in the Driver Breakout sessions were discussed and mapped in an interactive summary session to answer the following questions:

- Which gaps were identified by or are recognized by multiple Drivers and should lead to recommendations towards the ENTRUST Blueprint?
- Which gaps concern which use cases or are out of scope for the Blueprint?

This mapping between the gaps identified by the individual Drivers is included in the Results section as a summary table.

⁶ <https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

⁷ In the context of this deliverable, establishing a federation refers to establishing federated governance with common rules of engagements, standards and security requirements that ensure trust and interoperability within a network of TREs.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Driver 1: Federated Human Genomics as a catalyst for European TRE provision

4.1.1 Use case

Human genomic data are subject to strict national and international data protection regulations due to their **sensitive nature**. This presents challenges for **cross-border research** requiring access to distributed datasets while complying with legal and ethical frameworks of the respective data sources.

Such is our use-case, consisting in executing a common **Variant Calling over Binary Alignment Map (BAM) files hosted in separate TREs** (BSC's TRE and UNOTT's TRE), using a dataset located in EGA European Genome-Phenome Archive⁸ to identify specific biomarkers related to Colorectal Cancer.

This use case has been proposed in the context of a collaboration with WP19, in which the WP coordinators requested our help to provide a downsized example for the demonstrator they are developing. Since this first version of the demonstrator it's not expected to fully serve a federated analysis use case as it's limited to be a technical demonstrator (idoneity of the technical infrastructure and the technical interoperability of its components), WP19 plans to serve a federated analysis - data ingress, including aggregation, etc.- with the full use case we can provide, including multiple data types and vastly increasing the dataset used during analysis.

4.1.2 Usage patterns

Given the nature of our use case and our initial motivation, the most fitting usage pattern for this initial use case is **Q1**, where multiple **instances of the same dataset are analyzed in a federated manner**. This ensures that data remains within the jurisdiction of each TRE, enabling secure and collaborative research.

The definitive version of the use case may vary depending on the complexity allowed by the continuous iteration of the demonstrator; in general, a multi-omics analysis will directly jump to the **Q3** category as it will aggregate multiple non-overlapping datasets.

⁸ <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD50000000276>

4.1.3 User journey and gaps in generic user journey

In general, **the user journey matches our requirements** enabling and showcasing the flow of a genomic analysis. Nevertheless, as it stands, several gaps have been identified:

- **Dynamic Data Source Integration.**
 - The current framework does not allow researchers to add **new data sources** after project initiation.
 - This limitation forces researchers to **restart the registration process**, resulting in great inefficiencies.
- **Iterative Research Refinement.**
 - It does not properly represent the **iterative nature of research**, where the same analysis might require fine tuning or extra steps (e.g. data formatting) before the results can be considered to be mature.
 - This lack of support for **dynamic re-execution** before the export of results can be requested hinders researchers efficiency.

4.1.4 Gap analysis with Blueprint

Driver 1 has identified the following gaps:

- A central user registration system which keeps track of authorisations in different TREs. AAAI will support Single Sign On (SSO) over multiple TREs, but does not provide a system to register authorisations.
- Submitting and handling data requests is not covered in the ENTRUST Blueprint. There should be a standardised way to request access across resources / TREs. For health data, EHDS will provide such a standardised method to request data: each national HDAB will be responsible to implement a data request process⁹ and, in addition, a data request process will be implemented by the European Commission for requests that cover data residing in multiple member states.
- Driver 1 use cases require access to other genomic databases. Could this be resolved by pre-downloaded additional datasets? Usually it is known in advance which data is needed, but not always (e.g. developing pipeline, finding a problem). Alternative solutions would be to follow the data ingress process or allow access to limited external resources.

⁹ Data Access Application Management System or DAAMS

4.2 Driver 2: Common standards to enable trans-national sharing of administrative and social science data

4.2.1 Use case

Scientific Problem

Eight researchers provided a cross-country perspective to examine whether inaccurate teacher judgements of students' math skills correlate with student social origin and whether such bias is associated with math achievement in primary school, using education survey data from three separate countries. However, to illustrate the main issues around international research collaborations involving secure access data, we simplified our real world example down to 3 researchers, one from each country - making it a theoretical use case. We also assume that all datasets used were secondary use de-identified datasets, made available via TREs. Each researcher analysed the country-specific data in their TRE and local/national results were combined, after the local/national output checks and releases, for the cross-national perspective. The following user journey would have applied to this study:

1. Proposal - for cross-national research, users identify data sources needed in each country
2. User registration - x 3, one in each country
3. Project application - x 3, one in each country
4. Project approval - x 3, one in each country
5. User approval - x 3, one in each country
6. User training - x 3, one in each country
7. User gains access to TRE data source - x 3, one in each country
8. User conducts research with data source in TRE environment - x 3, one in each country
9. User makes request for output to be SDC checked - x 3, one in each country
10. Output approved - x 3, one in each country
11. Researchers can collaborate and combine results
12. Steps 8 to 11 repeated as often as necessary to achieve relevant and comparable results
13. Researchers can collaborate and combine results for finalised research paper outside TREs
14. Submission of paper for publication
15. Peer review
16. Possibly peer reviewer requests for edits/changes
17. If requests for edits/changes, steps 8-11 have to be repeated - x 3, in each country
18. Re-submission of paper for publication

19. Publication of the paper

Federation across the TREs according to the Blueprint would be highly beneficial in this use case, as steps 1-10 would only need to be completed once instead of three times (once for each country). This would make the application process less burdensome for researchers, allowing a more effective collaboration between research partners from different countries. This, however, would also require standardised metadata in the same language. As a result we would expect to see more international research carried out, addressing the global challenges of today and tomorrow.

Data and Sources

Data is at the individual level, and comes from social surveys or administration records. Data from each country is provided independently by data providers in each country, and access is also via the countries' own TREs.

Analytics

All standard quantitative research analytical approaches can be applied, such as regression analyses. Machine learning methods such as Large Language Models (LLMs) are not yet supported due to concerns over disclosure risk.

4.2.2 Usage patterns

The following usage patterns had been identified in the Blueprint:

“Analyses can use (Q0) a single dataset, (Q1) the same data from multiple regions, (Q2) different data types on the same individuals, or (Q3) multiple data types from multiple regions. Each dataset can have unique individual-level identifiers, with a separate master index providing the map (linkage spine) between dataset-specific identifiers and unique individuals.”

For our use case, Q3 applies as different, although similar datasets are used from all 3 different countries and include different individuals in each dataset.

4.2.3 User journey and gaps in generic user journey

The current Blueprint user journey used for the gap analysis (see Figure 2 in section 3.2.2) generally fits the user journeys of the Driver 2 TREs at the Driver partners. However, one exception is that the TRE at GESIS¹⁰, being much smaller, undertakes many of the tasks in the Data Holder layer as well as those in the TRE layer. Another exception is that ‘Installs pre-approved software’ and ‘Imports pre-approved data’, currently in the Data User layer, are done by both TREs. A final exception refers to the tasks carried out by the Data Access

¹⁰ [Secure Data Center - Access to sensitive data](#)

Committees (DACs). These are shown in the Data Holder layer, but for the UK Data Service (UKDS)¹¹, the DACs are external bodies linked to the data holders. Additional gaps identified are discussed in section 4.2.4.

4.2.4 Gap analysis with Blueprint

The Blueprint does cover many of the Driver 2 requirements and many of the recommendations would greatly improve TRE services. The main gaps between the requirements for Driver 2 and the ENTRUST Blueprint centre more on the user journey and service side of the process than TRE-internal elements (for the gap analysis summary table, see Appendix 1). The identified gaps are as follows:

- A maintained set of software and their packages that is regularly updated and augmented in a software service would be very welcome and would reduce a lot of work for individual TREs.
- Standardised terminology is needed across the Blueprint. The document includes differing definitions of pseudonymisation, exports, outputs, etc., which can be confusing, making cross-organisation communication open to misinterpretations.
- A dedicated User Support service (both at the TRE level and at the federation level) to support the user from data discovery to output control.
- Approvals process for all applications: all TREs have some kind of approval process and approvals can be given by different parties.
- Safe Researcher Training - for users and for TRE staff, with an electronic training record/researcher passport (electronic training records linked to the AAI are needed to make the TRE network interoperable).
- Processes to enable users to import their own or external data and code into the secure environment.
- Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) checks need to be built into the definition of export/output. Whilst export of results or output control is included in the Blueprint, there needs to be a more specific reference to SDC as all results outputs must undergo an SDC check before being released to the user. This is vital to ensure that no residual risk of disclosure exists in published results.
- Policies or processes to ensure data is properly cited.
- Archiving policy for users project folders - what should be archived and for how long (analysis datasets and/or code?).

In addition to these gaps, some recent developments are not covered in the Blueprint that could make federation easier. For example, the [SafePod network](#) has enabled an element of federation for secure data access in the UK, and RDC-Net will do the same in Germany but neither are considered in the ENTRUST Blueprint. In addition, the [International Data Access Network \(IDAN\)](#), a collaboration between several TREs in France, Germany, and the United

¹¹ <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/>

Kingdom facilitates cross-border research via the reciprocal provision of Safe Room Remote Access.

Additional factors to consider are the size of the TRE team and how high the usage is. These factors can impact which tasks fall within the TRE layer and which fall into the Data Holder layer. For example, the UKDS has several dedicated teams which handle different tasks associated with providing access to sensitive data. This means, for example, that the TRE team does not process applications, this is done by a separate 'data access' team, and the setting up of users' project areas is done by the technical team. In contrast, at GESIS, the TRE consists of just one full-time person and one part-time person who are solely responsible for these tasks.

4.3 Driver 3: Enabling the re-use of clinical trials data for research purposes across Europe

4.3.1 Use case: Individual participant data meta-analysis

Scientific problem

Individual participant data (IPD) meta-analysis of clinical trial data is a specific type of systematic review. Rather than extracting summary (aggregate) data from study publications or from investigators, the original research data are sought directly from the researchers responsible for each study. These data can then be re-analysed centrally and combined, if appropriate, in meta-analyses. IPD meta-analyses of clinical trial data enhance analytical potential, yielding more robust and reliable evidence^{12,13}. However, there are many hurdles for IPD meta-analyses, including the findability, the accessibility and the re-usability of datasets. This is caused by the low data sharing rates for IPD meta-analyses, which has been demonstrated in several studies and is still observed despite the various data sharing initiatives and platforms¹⁴. The use of TREs can significantly mitigate the challenges associated with IPD meta-analysis, by 1) facilitating secure, legally and ethically compliant cross-border re-use of clinical research data, improving data accessibility and sharing; 2) providing a secure environment for data analysis, alleviating concerns about data privacy and confidentiality; 3) promoting the use of consistent data standards and analytical methods across studies; 4) implementing standardised processes for data

¹² Stewart LA, Tierney JF. To IPD or not to IPD? Advantages and disadvantages of systematic reviews using individual patient data. *Eval Health Prof.* 2002 Mar;25(1):76-97. doi: 10.1177/0163278702025001006. PMID: 11868447.

¹³ <https://methods.cochrane.org/ipdma/about-ipd-meta-analyses>

¹⁴ Ohmann C, Moher D, Siebert M, Motschall E, Naudet F. Status, use and impact of sharing individual participant data from clinical trials: a scoping review. *BMJ Open.* 2021 Aug 18;11(8):e049228. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2021-049228. PMID: 34408052; PMCID: PMC8375721.

validation, completeness checks and error detection which can enhance the overall quality of data used in IPD meta-analyses, addressing issues related to data integrity and inconsistencies; and 5) fostering collaboration.

Data and sources

IPD meta-analysis combine raw data from each specific participant from multiple studies into a single dataset for further analysis, offering a more detailed and flexible approach to evidence synthesis compared to study level meta-analyses that combine estimates from multiple studies to generate a summary estimate^{15,16}. The data types may include participants' demographics (e.g. age, sex), medical history, vital sign measurements, lab and diagnostics findings, treatment details, adverse events, clinical outcomes. The data sources on the other hand, may be the original trial investigators, data-sharing repositories, data-sharing initiatives, published and unpublished data.

Analytics

The type of analytics that can be performed include:

- Statistical approaches (one-stage and two-stage)
- Advanced analytics (subgroup analysis, intervention effects, missing data, etc)

4.3.2 Usage patterns

Driver 3 works to identify and overcome challenges in sharing and reusing data within the clinical research community. The usage pattern for the use case described above which involves individual-level sensitive data, falls within the usage pattern (Q1), same type of data from multiple regions, which in our case would translate into analyses between different clinical trials datasets.

Other usage patterns that we expect to apply in Driver 3, include, direct dataset reuse, which fits Q0 (data from one dataset within a single region) and, combining clinical trial data with health care data from the same individuals, fitting Q2/Q3 (multiple data types within the same or multiple regions).

4.3.3 User journey and gaps in generic user journey

Driver 3 generic user journey (Fig 4) covers the scenario in which the re-user wants, for a specific research project, to access and analyse a clinical trial dataset that is stored in a

¹⁵ Ventresca M, et al. Obtaining and managing data sets for individual participant data meta-analysis: scoping review and practical guide. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2020 May 12;20(1):113. doi: 10.1186/s12874-020-00964-6. PMID: 32398016; PMCID: PMC7218569.

¹⁶ Riley RD, Lambert PC, Abo-Zaid G. Meta-analysis of individual participant data: rationale, conduct, and reporting. *BMJ*. 2010 Feb 5;340:c221. doi: 10.1136/bmj.c221. PMID: 20139215.

TRE. This user journey involves data discovery, project application, user training in information governance (IG), data access and analysis, handling output requests, and publishing with data credit attribution. The steps are based on the processes implemented by ECRIN and TSD in the context of the clinical research Data Sharing Repository (crDSR). Although these steps are generalisable enough to apply to most clinical trial data sharing scenarios that use a TRE¹⁷, specific requirements of data providers / TREs / data re-users often apply.

Figure 4: Expected user journey for re-users of clinical trial data in a TRE. In orange: journey steps requiring user actions. In blue: journey steps requiring TRE actions.

In the use case of IPD meta-analysis, the re-users or meta-analysis specialists will need to access multiple clinical trial datasets stored in different locations (e.g., institutional repositories, hosting TREs, clinical trial sponsors' local infrastructure).

Challenges for this type of federated use scenario were fine-tuned capitalising on the presentations and discussions held during the IPD meta-analysis workshop organised by ECRIN on 15 January 2025 and later in the Blueprint Validation workshop in Utrecht, where the merits of pooling datasets in one single TRE vs distributed querying were discussed.

Data discovery

In relation to our use case, IPD meta-analysis, using a TREs for identifying clinical studies suitable for IPD meta-analysis (data discovery) presents some challenges but also potential benefits.

In the traditional approach to IPD meta-analysis, researchers usually already have a list of relevant studies, or find them querying clinical trial registries like ClinicalTrials.gov and WHO ICTRP, or they may use other sources like the crMDR. Registries contain (standardised) and

¹⁷ Pellen C, Le Louarn A, Spurrier-Bernard G, Decullier E, Chrétien JM, Rosenthal E, Le Goff G, Moher D, Ioannidis JPA, Naudet F. Ten (not so) simple rules for clinical trial data-sharing. *PLoS Comput Biol.* 2023 Mar 9;19(3):e1010879. doi: 10.1371/journal.pcbi.1010879. PMID: 36893146; PMCID: PMC9997951.

open metadata of clinical trials/clinical studies. This task is usually performed as preparation for the IPD-meta-analysis outside the TRE. Challenges appear when clinical studies are not registered in usual registries and are hard to find, and in such cases, distributed query in a TRE will be of little help, even if registries are available within the TRE. The functionality would thus be of little value for identification of clinical trials/clinical studies.

A federated query could be useful if it helps identify studies that can provide IPD through the TRE. This assumes that IPD data is either already stored within the TRE, or accessible through the TRE (which introduces additional complexity).

If a TRE were federated with data sources like Vivli (a clinical trial registry), researchers could search metadata of clinical trials/clinical studies directly through the TRE and explore IPD access options for studies in those sources. So, if several data sources would be linked to the TRE (including crMDR), a federated query could simplify study identification, providing a single access point for researchers, reducing the need to check multiple registries separately.

Data requests

Once relevant clinical studies or trials have been identified for an IPD meta-analysis, the next step is to request access to the data. There are two main approaches:

- **Option 1:** Direct contact with sponsors/principal investigators. Researchers must identify and reach out to the relevant contacts. This often requires multiple attempts via email or phone, with responses being delayed or fragmented. Along with IPD, researchers often request additional trial-related documents (e.g., trial protocols, case report forms, trial reports) to understand the study's context.
- **Option 2:** Requesting data via a repository. The data request follows the process defined by the specific repository. Challenges include rapidly changing data-sharing policies of organizations and repositories, complex and time-consuming procedures for submitting requests.

Can a federated TRE help with Data Requests? Not for Option 1, as this requires personal communication. For repository-based requests (Option 2), even if a trial repository is linked to the TRE, researchers must still follow each repository's specific request procedures. If multiple repositories are involved, the process can become lengthy and resource-intensive. The only way a federated TRE infrastructure could simplify this process for the researcher, is if trial repositories federate and establish harmonised rules for data requests.

Data access

Data access is dependent on the type of IPD meta-analyses. There are two statistical approaches for conducting an IPD meta-analysis:

- **One-Stage:** Analyzes IPD from all studies simultaneously using models such as hierarchical regression with random effects. This approach is preferred when studies have small sample sizes since it provides a more accurate likelihood estimation.
- **Two-Stage:** First, aggregated data (e.g., effect estimates) are generated separately for each study, then combined using a traditional meta-analysis model¹⁸.

Both approaches are widely used, and the choice depends on the context, and researchers can choose either approach, carefully following best practice¹⁹.

At the Utrecht meeting, a classification of five different models for accessing and analyzing IPD in a federated TRE network was proposed:

1. **Classic Stage 1 "data pooling" (Model 1):** The IPD from all trials (available in TREs) are pooled in a single TRE within the federated network. Unlike Model 2, all data transfers and analyses are performed within the federated TRE network.
2. **Classic Stage 2 (Model 2):** Each IPD dataset is accessed within its own TRE and analyses are performed in the analytical zone of this TRE. Aggregated (and anonymous) results from individual studies are then combined (as in the classical stage 2 model) inside or outside the federated TRE network.
3. **Data view (Model 3):** A single TRE (the "host") provides a view of IPD from multiple trials in the federated network, allowing the researcher to view and interact with the data depending on how the data are presented to them and in what tool. A virtual table is created from different sources, but full analysis will depend on the presenting tool. If the presenting tool allows full analyses to be run on the view, then the researcher can apply the full power of whatever desktop tools they have. It's up to the hosting TRE (and project governance) to decide what the researcher can and can't do; the federation just enables the dataset to be presented as a single thing. This model is a simpler version of Model 4, and it is useful when remote queries can be easily encapsulated in a single message and datasets are nice and tabular.
4. **Remote execution (Model 4):** The analysis is initiated in one TRE (the "host" TRE), but it uses a job-submission model to send remote execution requests to access IPD stored in multiple other TREs within the federated network. More advanced than Model 3, allowing complex multi-trial analyses without direct data movement: the submitted jobs may be complex workflows retrieved from workflow repositories, either ahead of time or dynamically at job submission.

¹⁸ Burke DL, Ensor J, Riley RD. Meta-analysis using individual participant data: one-stage and two-stage approaches, and why they may differ. *Stat Med.* 2017 Feb 28;36(5):855-875. doi: 10.1002/sim.7141. Epub 2016 Oct 16. PMID: 27747915; PMCID: PMC5297998.

¹⁹ Riley RD, Ensor J, Hattle M, Papadimitropoulou K, Morris TP. Two-stage or not two-stage? That is the question for IPD meta-analysis projects. *Res Synth Methods.* 2023 Nov;14(6):903-910. doi: 10.1002/jrsm.1661. Epub 2023 Aug 22. PMID: 37606180; PMCID: PMC7615283.

This highlights the main difference between Model 3 and Model 4, which comes down to the complexity of the query sent between TREs. Model 3 works with simple queries that can be directly sent from TRE A to TRE B, while Model 4 handles more complex queries that can't be packaged as a simple message. Instead, TRE A asks TRE B to run a specific workflow provided by a third-party service (e.g. Software Service C). Thus Model 4 adds an extra layer by involving a third party to handle complex workflows, while Model 3 relies on straightforward, direct queries.

5. **“Eyes-off” remote execution (Model 5):** A refinement of Model 4, where the individual IPD datasets are “hidden” behind APIs which only allow certain queries to be processed and which never expose individual-level data to the research user. .

For a TRE to access IPD, the data must either be transferred to the TRE or linked to the external trial repository or trial database. Since IPD from clinical trials is sensitive data, several requirements, in addition to the general ones (e.g., register at TRE, login), must be met if the data is transferred into a TRE, such as:

- Data sharing policy (e.g. R018)
- Data transfer agreement
- Data use agreement
- Data analysis
- Data publishing and archiving
- Data backup
- Disclosure control

If a trial repository itself functions as a TRE and is part of a federated TRE network, a standardised data transfer process could be implemented. However, for this to be effective, it would require multiple repositories to adopt the same approach. It is however unlikely that most trial repositories will function as TREs according to the guidelines and standards defined in EOSC-ENTRUST. As a result, the physical transfer of IPD into a TRE remains the most feasible option at this stage.

Data management and analysis

For effective data analysis within a federated network of TREs, researchers need access to a range of statistical software packages (e.g., R, SAS). Researchers may also want to use their own packages or analysis tools, which could require a pre-approval process to ensure such tools can be used for analysis in the TRE. Since IPD is often shared in different formats and different degrees of anonymisation, there is a need to standardize variables and outcomes across different trials. Therefore, exact definitions are needed from each trial (annotated CRFs, codebooks, data dictionaries).

To conduct an IPD meta-analysis accurately, researchers may also require that other trial-related objects/documents (e.g. study protocol, informed consent form, study reports)

be also available within the TRE. The availability of these objects depends on whether they are stored in the trial repository or provided directly by the sponsor/PI.

To understand specific issues (e.g. reasons for missing data, data related to patients excluded post-randomization), the information available in the TRE might be insufficient. In such cases, direct contact with individuals that know the data (e.g., statisticians, data managers, PIs) is often necessary to clarify inconsistencies.

The choice between performing a stage 1 (model 1) or stage 2 (model 2) IPD meta-analysis depends on the availability of IPD within the federated TRE network. If IPD from all required studies is available within the TRE network, a full stage 1 analysis can be performed. If all studies are in separate locations outside the network, a stage 2 model with separate analysis of each study followed by aggregation of results can be performed.

Disclosure control

Output and disclosure control is a necessary requirement for any IPD meta-analysis. It must be assured that individual persons are not re-identifiable. Results from IPD meta-analysis are usually public and the data privacy risk should be neglectable.

4.3.4 Gap analysis with Blueprint

Gaps identified during the validation workshop

During the Blueprint validation workshop, the gap analysis of Driver 3 identified the following gaps in relation to the use case:

Governance and Regulatory Gaps

- Lack of federated governance, with no clear structure for a federated governance across TREs, although it's implicitly assumed.
- Complex regulatory environment where regulations vary across countries, making data sharing agreements complex and slow, especially with pseudonymised data under GDPR.
- Incomplete consent forms: informed consent often doesn't cover data sharing, creating legal hurdles.

Data Access and Sharing

- Reluctance to move data across borders due to privacy and regulatory concerns.
- Fragmented data sources, where researchers face difficulties contacting multiple data holders individually.
- Limited integration with non-TRE repositories, meaning that external repositories (like Vivli) may not meet TRE standards, limiting seamless integration.

Technical and data management

- Complex query execution between TREs (difference between Models 3, 4 and 5).
- Workflows are not automated, increasing manual effort and potential for errors.
- Software compatibility, when "Bring code to data" models require software adaptation and inspection.
- Metadata discovery limitations due to lack of a unified metadata catalog across TREs for easy data discovery²⁰.
- Inconsistent data standardization which might be present in clinical trial data, with varying data formats and anonymization levels that complicate cross-study analyses.
- Disclosure control to prevent the unintended release of sensitive or identifiable information when sharing or analyzing data remains unaddressed. Plans to address this only in future phases.

Operational and Workflow

- No standardized process for project approval yet.
- Data volume and simultaneous data processing across multiple TREs might be complex.

User Experience

- Lack of a central entry point on the level of a TRE federation might be cumbersome for researchers that need to engage with multiple TREs and repositories separately.

4.4 Driver 4: Public-Private interactions between TRE in health and environmental data

4.4.1 Use case

Scientific problem

Private companies can be interested to collaborate with research institutions and universities for multiple reasons, for example to study a scientific problem which is of interest to the company or to co-create revolutionary innovations. This use case focuses on a long-term (multi-year) research, development and innovation (RDI) relationship between a university and a company in the sports industry, which for the purposes of this use case are called University and Sports Academy.

²⁰ For health data, EHDS will provide an EU-wide metadata catalogue to support discovery.

Sports Academy is a company that offers two types of services for sports clubs and athletes. Their core business has evolved around training centers where sports clubs of different levels (including national level) can organize intensive training camps or individual athletes practice their skills. As part of their core business, Sports Academy has collected information on individual athletes as well as sport clubs that collaborate with them. Data related to training has been gathered continuously in various sites. As their business evolved they realized that these datasets could be used to create digital services for sport clubs, their coaches and athletes to improve their training practices and outcomes. To develop their services further, Sports Academy contacted University and proposed a cooperation to develop them. University was interested in this possibility and thus started their long-term RDI relationship.

In recent years this cooperation has transformed from digital service development toward data-driven research collaboration. To accelerate this the need for creating synthetic data has been identified. Thus, the research question for this use case is *'How to create synthetic data that is representative enough to be used in AI development while not revealing actual personal data?'*

Data and sources

- Source data originates from a company that offers solutions for sport clubs and their coaches to improve their training methods and outcomes.
- Data includes three types of data regarding the athletes: user information (e.g. name, date of birth), event specific information (e.g. event type, place, time), and tracking information (e.g. performance durability test scores, results of game analysis, psychosocial test scores).
- Data is standardized.
- Data is stored on a secure server offered by a private cloud provider.
- PI of the research project has access to data on the basis of a contract between University (the data processor) and Sports Academy (the data holder).

Analytics

To create synthetic data based on the original data, data should be transferred to a TRE. The data analysis requires a Research Analytics Zone²¹ offered by the TRE.

²¹ The Research Analytics Zone (RAZ) defined in the ENTRUST Blueprint provides users with a workspace to process data in a secure way. The definition of RAZ shows similarities to a Secure Processing Environment (SPE), as prescribed by the EHDS Regulation and defined by Tehdas2 as a highly protected digital environment where authorized users can analyse health data for purposes defined in the EHDS regulation. Further discussions are needed to map EHDS business capabilities on the ENTRUST Blueprint to ensure compliance.

4.4.2 Usage patterns

The usage patterns included in the Blueprint do not seem to include the usage pattern for this use case. Usage pattern Q0 appears to be the most appropriate but it is limited to analyses of a single dataset. In this case there are multiple data sets which are analysed in the same TRE.

Although this use case is limited to data analyses in one TRE, the use of multiple TREs according to the usage pattern Q2 is of interest for future research.

4.4.3 User journey and gaps in generic user journey

The generic user journey does not recognize the use case where users have access to the data before they start using TRE. In this use case users need the TRE to securely analyse the data set and store the original data set as well as the analysed data set in a secured environment. In addition, it is relevant to this use case that creation of a research project is included as a separate step in the generic user journey.

The generic user journey was modified to better fit the needs of this use case and is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: User journey adapted to Driver 4.

4.4.4 Gap analysis with Blueprint

Requirements for Driver 4 were identified and mapped with SATRE prior to the workshop and they are included in the Drivers List of requirements (Appendix 2).

Gaps identified during the workshop

During the workshop, Driver 4 focused on validating the Blueprint from the viewpoint of this use case and identifying possible gaps in it. In general, the Blueprint was well suited for this use case and included aspects that are relevant for it. For example, the Blueprint acknowledges that a PI can use TRE to analyse data that they already have accessed. Thus, they have the right to import data to TRE and export it.

Some gaps in relation to the use case were also found during the workshop. They are: proprietary data and software, sandbox approach and disclosing metadata.

Proprietary data and software

For this use case it is relevant to acknowledge that collaboration with private companies could require that proprietary data can be analysed within TRE. Also proprietary software might need to be installed in TRE.

Sandbox approach

One key requirement for Driver 4 has been internet access within TRE. This possibility is generally lacking in TREs due to strict policies which can be dictated by local or regional laws. However, in this use case data law itself would not prevent internet access within TRE, thus internet access within TRE would be desired by researchers which would enable accessing required resources without the help of TRE. It was discussed during the workshop how this access should be implemented without causing a risk to the TRE's infrastructure, data sources and other users. One option suggested was a sandbox approach which would allow accessing the internet and downloading content for those virtual machines that are assigned for the individual research project. However, other parts of the infrastructure would not be affected by anything that would happen in the sandbox. Thus, any negative outcomes would be limited to the individual research project. Since access to external resources from TREs is also a well-known issue within the HPC community, solutions developed there will also be investigated.

Disclosing metadata

In this use case, source data might not have metadata before it is stored and analysed in TRE. Thus, the metadata might need to be created de novo. To do this researchers as well as data holders could need some training on FAIR data. Although the aim is to make data FAIR, it should be possible to keep metadata disclosed only for those who have the right to access the data. Possibility to disclose metadata is important in the case of a collaboration with a company.

5. Results & Discussion

5.1 Drivers use cases

The Drivers described the following use cases:

Driver 1

Research Question: Identifying specific biomarkers related to Colorectal Cancer

Data: Binary Alignment Map (BAM) files hosted in separate TREs within EGA²² (BSC's TRE and UNOTT's TRE)

Analysis: Common Variant Calling over different data sets hosted in separate TREs

Usage Pattern: Q1

Driver 2

Research Question: Do inaccurate teacher judgements of students' math skills correlate with student social origin and is such bias associated with math achievement in primary school?

Analysis: Standard quantitative research analytical approaches

Data: Education survey data from 3 countries.

Usage Pattern: Q1

Driver 3

Research Question: Individual participant data (IPD) meta-analysis over clinical trials. IPD meta-analysis combines raw data from each specific participant from multiple studies into a single dataset for further analysis

Data: Raw individual participant data from multiple clinical trials

Analysis: Statistical approaches (one-stage and two-stage) and advanced analytics (subgroup analysis, intervention effects, missing data, etc)

Usage Pattern: Q1

Driver 4

Research Question: How to create synthetic data within a public-private collaboration that is representative enough to be used in AI development while not revealing actual personal data?

Data: Different types of data on athletes' health and performance, held by a commercial party

Analysis: Synthetic data generation based on real world data

²² <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD5000000276>

Usage Pattern: none really applied but Q0 seemed to be closest

Usage patterns

Three out of four use cases described a usage pattern Q1, where the same data from different data subjects is spread out over different regions (countries, TREs, or any other governance region). It is therefore to be expected that the gaps and requirements identified in the gap analysis will largely concern issues with combining data from different subjects over TREs. One use case describes usage pattern Q0, where interoperability challenges might be less pressing. For this use case, securely sharing data with commercial parties is addressed. Table 1 shows the usage patterns that are found in the Drivers' use cases as well as those expected by the Drivers in the future. Usage patterns that require data to be linked on the individual subject level (Q2 and Q3) are expected by most Drivers. Therefore, the requirements that these usage patterns pose for the ENTRUST Blueprint should be assessed at a later stage.

Table 1: Usage patterns described in the Drivers' use cases and those expected in the future or for other potential use cases within the Drivers.

	Driver 1	Driver 2	Driver 3	Driver 4
Q0	x	expected	expected	use case
Q1	use case	use case	use case	
Q2		expected	expected	expected
Q3	expected	expected	expected	

Users

Table 2 shows the users that were identified in the M7.1 milestone report (black text), augmented with the users that were identified in the Drivers' use cases and the discussions during the Blueprint Validation Workshop (orange text). Since discussions about processes and federation services brought up users that have less direct interaction with the TRE itself, we added a gradient to the user categories, from the data users, who directly interact with the TRE, to regulatory bodies, who might never directly interact with the TRE, save for auditing purposes.

Table 2: User categories and users identified by the Drivers, mapped from direct to indirect interaction with the TRE. Users that were added through use cases and discussions in the Blueprint Validation workshop are shown in orange.

Direct interaction -----> Indirect interaction

Data users	Data providers	Infrastructure providers	Regulatory bodies
Researchers (PIs, project members)	Data managers	TRE Administrators	Auditors
Policy makers	Data custodians	Federation administrators	
Patients	PIs	User support staff	
Citizens	Trial sponsors		
Employees of commercial parties	Healthcare professionals		
	Public health institutes		
	Companies		

5.2 Gap analysis

The Drivers' gap analysis was designed to identify gaps between the ENTRUST Blueprint and the Drivers' requirements. Because the generic user journey and the Drivers' use cases were used as a basis for the gap analysis, the process also identified gaps in the generic user journey and additional requirements for the Drivers. In this section, we report the main findings from the gap analysis. The full summary table with gaps and requirements identified by the Drivers can be found in Appendix 1.

5.2.1 User Journey Gaps

The gaps that Drivers identified in the user journey included gaps in its ordering and iterative nature, scope and the roles defined. An important gap is the focus of the user journey on using data from a single TRE, while the use cases of the Drivers mostly concern data analysis over multiple TREs.

Gaps in the ordering and iteration

- 'Discover data' should be the first step
- User journey should allow for a non-linear analysis process and re-execution
- User journey should allow researchers to add new data sources after project initiation.

Missing steps

- Cost management and payment
- 'Project start' (Driver 3 and 4)
- Assigning different user roles by admin

Gaps in the scope

- Analysis over multiple TREs
- User journey should cover two different types of use cases: 1) user discover data; 2) user uploads data in TRE

Gaps in role definition and terminology

- Green and blue user flows not distinct for all Drivers, this should be accounted for
- The focus should not be on export of data, but on Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) (Driver 3)
- Pseudonymisation is too narrow a term - factually anonymised (GESIS) or de-identified (UKDS) is more accurate (Driver 2)
- Most TREs do not allow self-installation of software and this does not fit the software service component of the Blueprint.
- Use 'archive project space' instead of 'close project space', so it can be reinstated if needed (e.g. following a peer review resulting in further requests)

The gap analysis of the user journey revealed several critical areas needing improvement. Key gaps include the need for a more iterative and flexible analysis process, starting with data discovery and allowing for non-linear workflows and the addition of new data sources post-project initiation. Missing steps such as cost management and project initiation were also highlighted. The scope should be expanded to support analysis across multiple TREs and accommodate both data discovery and data upload use cases. Paragraph 5.2.2 addresses these gaps by proposing a revised user journey that aligns more closely with the Drivers' use cases.

5.2.2 Updated user journey

Figure 6 depicts the revised generic user journey. This version of the user journey supports data analysis over multiple TREs by including an additional role from the ENTRUST Blueprint, the *Federation Governance* actor. Other role names have also been harmonized with the Blueprint. Some Drivers noted that the *TRE Governance* and *Data Controller* roles might overlap in smaller TREs. In these cases, the TRE Governance acts as the data controller and thus also performs their actions. To comply with GDPR, however, it remains important to distinguish the *Data Controller* role, as it comes with unique responsibilities.

In addition to the added steps and roles, the user journey has been restructured for readability with an overarching journey consisting of six steps that closely matches the EHDS user journey. Steps for the different roles are plotted under each overarching step without making assumptions about the precise order, to allow for differences between Drivers and Provider implementations.

Figure 6: Revised generic user journey. The role of *Federation Governance* was added to account for cross-TRE use cases. Color coding as in the user journey depicted in Figure 2: orange: *Data user*; yellow: *Federation Governance*; blue: *TRE Governance*; green: *Data Controller*. Overarching steps in the user journey are depicted in grey, sub-steps are plotted on the different roles under each overarching step. Order between sub-steps is not depicted for clarity and to allow for differences between Drivers/ use cases and TRE Providers. This user journey does not include the role of Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs) that are tasked with receiving and evaluating health data access requests and issuing health data permits. HDABs will take over some of the tasks of Federation Governance, TRE governance and even Data holders. This will be taken integrated into later iterations of the user journey.

5.2.3 Blueprint Gaps

Table 3 shows the gaps between the Drivers' requirements and the year-one version of the ENTRUST Blueprint identified during the gap analysis sessions during the Blueprint Validation Workshop. The relevance of each gap for each Driver is indicated in the rightmost four columns, to allow us to assess which gaps are recognized across Drivers and which might be specific to a Driver or even a use case.

Two important gaps were identified and agreed on by all Drivers that would require a component to be added to the Blueprint:

- Data access application
- Management of data access agreements

Table 3: Gaps between the refined Drivers requirements and the year-one version of the ENTRUST Blueprint. In the four columns on the right the Drivers indicated whether the gap is relevant to each Driver. D1: Driver 1; D2: Driver 2; D3: Driver 3; D4: Driver 4

No	Gap	D1	D2	D3	D4
1	Standardised terminology is needed across the Blueprint, ideally externally published so they can be referred to in the community		☐		☐
2	Lack of federated governance, with no clear structure for a federated governance across TREs, although it's implicitly assumed			☐	
3	A dedicated User Support service to support the user from data discovery to output control		☐		☐
4	Adopt a metadata standard and agree on a minimal set of metadata about a dataset on the federation level	☐	☐	☐	☐
5	Federation needs a unified metadata catalog across TREs for easy data discovery			☐	
6	Standardized data access request process that supports requesting data from multiple TREs	☐	☐	☐	☐
7	Single point of access for data access requests	☐		☐	
8	Unified approval process for all data access applications		☐	☐	
9	Analysis over multiple TREs requires ad hoc data access committees involving all data owners	☐	☐	☐	☐
10	Unified procedures and single point of access for signing data use agreements with multiple TREs	☐	☐	☐	☐
11	Federation-level registry for agreements			☐	
12	The Blueprint needs to allow for automation of workflows			☐	

13	Limited integration with external non-TRE repositories			☐	
14	Extended functionality of the query management zone to allow for federated learning	☐		☐	
15	Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) checks need to be built into the definition of output control in the Blueprint		☐	☐	☐
16	The data controller needs to make the decision about export of results under GDPR ²³ . This needs to be represented in the actors connected to the role of output controller				☐

5.2.4 Identified requirements

The gap analysis performed by the Drivers during the Blueprint Validation Workshop revealed additional requirements for Blueprint components. These requirements are not identified as gaps, since they are implicitly included in the Blueprint when the functional component that might support the requirement is defined in the Blueprint. Therefore, the additional requirements for Blueprint components identified in the gap analysis might not lead to an extension of the Blueprint architecture, but might inform the future Operating Procedures or serve as a guideline for TREs developing these components as well as the demonstrators / solutions developed in WP16 and WP19.

Discovery Service

- Data discovery over multiple TREs should be available through a unified service portal (all Drivers)
- Data sharing policy from multiple TREs accessible through central service portal in federation (all Drivers)
- Synthetic data as help for data discovery (Driver 4)

AAAI

- Central registration system in a unified service portal: this should allow users to register at a central point in the federation as a means to register to all TREs within it. The central registration is not a property of AAAI, but should be linked to the AAAI service in order to keep track of users' authorisations within the federation.

²³ This might change with EHDS. Here, HDAB has responsibilities with regard to oversight of SPEs and might therefore fulfill the role of output controller in some cases. However, details need to be worked out in implementation acts, expected beginning 2027.

- Should allow for authentication of non-European users who do not have access to eID²⁴ or nationals from EU countries where national regulations do not support eID or where there are restrictions on which countries within EU are trusted
- User training and certification should be included in AAAI (“Researcher passport”)
- There could be specific criteria for the authentication methods, such as biometrics etc.
- Entitlements based on contracts between TREs and commercial parties (Driver 4)

User training

User training was an important requirement posed by all Drivers. It should be noted, however, that in a TRE federation not all training needs to be provided by individual TRE providers. Some training (for example *Safe Researcher Training*), could be offered at the federation level.

- Should address the issue and awareness of data transfer to a 3rd country (all Drivers)
- Ongoing user support must be available during the project (Driver 2)
- Training for researchers + for TRE staff (all Drivers)
- Training and communication about FAIR²⁵ data for researchers and company representatives (Driver 4)

Software Service

Use cases might need software not available within the federation or self-developed software. The gap analysis showed that (controlled) self-installation of software through whitelisting of internet domains might not be the best solution for this within a federation. An open internet connection interferes with the security of the TRE. To address the need for proprietary software, the Software Service should include:

- A maintained set of software and their packages that is regularly updated and augmented
- Synchronisation of software repositories to the TRE
- A checking process for packages requested by users that are not on list

For the use of Public data repositories through the Software Service, the following requirements were identified by Driver 1 in the gap analysis:

- Should support access to external genomic databases / reference datasets

²⁴ eID is a set of services provided by the European Commission to enable the mutual recognition of national electronic identification schemes (eID) across borders. It allows European citizens to use their national eIDs when accessing online services from other European countries. Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-building-blocks/sites/display/DIGITAL/eID>

²⁵ The FAIR framework provides principles to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR). See: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

- Should support ingress of/ access to additional data at any time during the project

Disclosure Control

- Data controller needs to make the decision under GDPR, while a Health Data Access Body (HDAB²⁶) might have that role under EHDS. This needs to be represented in the actors connected to the role of output controller
- A secure way to release ML/AI models to other TREs within the federation for training ML/AI over data in multiple TREs
- Guideline for disclosure control for other types of sensitive data: IPR, commercial, military, potential for harm, etc. (Driver 4)
- Investigate whether agreements can be made at the federation level to allow models or data to move to other TREs in the federation without SDC for training ML/AI over data in multiple TREs

5.3 Recommendations towards the ENTRUST Blueprint

Based on the gap analysis, as well as discussions during the Blueprint Validation Workshop and beyond, we have identified key recommendations for the next version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint. The recommendations focus on four critical areas: architecture, standards, processes, and alignment with EHDS and EOSC on all of these.

Architecture

1. **Federated Governance Structure:** Establish a clear and formalized federated governance structure with defined roles, responsibilities, and processes to ensure cohesive management across TREs. SafePod Network in UK is an example that is well accepted by data owners and that could be a stepping stone towards a Federation. Establish under which models federated data access and analysis can be performed (see section 4.3.3 for a description of the models).
2. **Central Access Point:** Implement a central access point for user registration and training, data discovery (implemented as a unified metadata catalogue), data access applications, and managing contractual agreements between multiple parties, supported by unified processes and federation-level governance.

Standards

1. **Standardized Terminology:** The EOSC-ENTRUST glossary is currently under development by the Architecture WP. Finalizing and publishing the glossary is essential to agreeing on a common terminology.
2. **Metadata Standard:** Adopt a metadata standard (preferably interoperable with EHDS, which will use DCAT-AP²⁷) and agree on a minimal set of metadata for

²⁶ European Health Data Space (EHDS) Article 36, Health data access bodies:

[https://www.european-health-data-space.com/European_Health_Data_Space_Article_36_\(Proposal_3.5.2022\).html](https://www.european-health-data-space.com/European_Health_Data_Space_Article_36_(Proposal_3.5.2022).html)

²⁷ <https://healthdcat-ap.github.io/>

datasets at the federation level to facilitate easier data discovery.

Processes

1. **Data Access Request:** Develop a unified procedure at the federation level for submitting and evaluating data access requests to multiple TREs. This procedure should include: (i) a harmonized request form, (ii) a process to form an ad hoc data access committee involving all data owners and (iii) a unified approval process. This unified procedure should be in line with the EHDS regulation, such that, once EHDS is implemented, connection to EHDS procedures for data access requests can fulfill this requirement for health data.
2. **User Support and Training:** Implement a dedicated user support service to assist users from data discovery through to output control, and provide comprehensive training programs for all roles in the federation, including unified safe researcher training and certification. It must be noted that the lack of funding and staff might limit the user support and training resources at TREs.

Alignment with EHDS and EOSC

1. **Federated Architecture:**
 - a. *Align with the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) Blueprint²⁸ and Simpl²⁹.* Both the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and EHDS employ a federated architecture. An EOSC-ENTRUST federation should align with both in order to realise interoperability, not only within, but also across data spaces. Adopting architecture frameworks that lay the groundwork for building federated data spaces irrespective of research domain, such as the DSSC Blueprint. The DSSC Blueprint supports the development of a federated architecture that allows different data spaces to interconnect and share resources. Aligning with this architecture greatly enhances interoperability of EOSC-ENTRUST with both EOSC and EHDS. On the technical level, Simpl can play a crucial role in enhancing interoperability of EOSC-ENTRUST with both EOSC and EHDS. Simpl is an open-source middleware platform that supports data access and interoperability among European data spaces, ensuring seamless data flow and compliance with regulations.
 - b. *Align with EHDS central services and EOSC ecosystem.* EHDS will provide a central access point for data discovery and data access applications, as well as a central SPE. In addition, the EOSC EU node³⁰ provides data sharing services, such as a compute node with an underlying payment system.

²⁸ <https://dssc.eu/page/blueprint>

²⁹ <https://simpl-programme.ec.europa.eu/>

³⁰ [Home | European Open Science Cloud - EU Node](#)

Finally, the EOSC SIESTA³¹ and TITAN³² projects both contribute to secure re-use of sensitive data, with SIESTA focusing more on data exchange, while the focus of TITAN is primarily on the development of an open-source software platform. By aligning with these initiatives, the aim of a central access point can be reached in an effective and interoperable way.

2. **Standards:** Adopt standards that are interoperable with EHDS, such as DCAT-AP, where health data is concerned and align with standards used in EOSC for social and environmental data to ensure interoperability with both data spaces. For cross-dataspace terms, DSSC also provides a glossary³³.
3. **Processes:** Align with EHDS and EOSC for data access requests and training. EHDS will provide a unified process for submitting and evaluating data access requests, including a standardised request form. Although HDABs will play a key role in evaluating data access requests submitted through EHDS, EOSC-ENTRUST can already ensure interoperability with EHDS by aligning with the EHDS standard request form released on the HealthData@EU Central Platform³⁴. HDABs in EU member states will be responsible for training delivery to users. Therefore, aligning with HDABs on safe researcher training might relieve some of the resources within the TREs. Beyond EHDS and health data, EOSC Data Commons³⁵ aims to establish services for inter- and cross-disciplinary data discovery, access, sharing and reuse in the EOSC Federation, whereas training could be provided through the EOSC EU Node.

6. Conclusions & Impact

The use cases and usage patterns described by the Drivers highlight the diverse requirements for TREs. The Q1 usage pattern, prevalent in most use cases, underscores the need for federated data access over multiple TREs. As future use cases are expected to involve usage patterns that pose more complex data linkage requirements (Q2 and Q3), the ENTRUST Blueprint must evolve to address these challenges. Additionally, the varied user categories identified emphasize the importance of clear definitions for roles and actors in the Blueprint.

The gaps in the generic user journey were addressed by presenting a new iteration. This iteration of the user journey will inform the next versions of the Drivers set of requirements and the ENTRUST Blueprint. As the Drivers' use cases evolve and become more detailed, further updates to the user journey might follow.

³¹ <https://eosc-siesta.eu/project/>

³² <https://titan-eosc.eu/>

³³ [DSSC Glossary | Version 2.0 | September 2023 - Glossary - Data Spaces Support Centre](#)

³⁴ [HealthData@EU](#)

³⁵ [EOSC Data Commons - EOSC Association](#)

The gap analysis revealed two gaps in the first version of the ENTRUST Blueprint that necessitate adding new capabilities: Data access application and Management of data access agreements. Furthermore, an overarching picture emerges where the ENTRUST Blueprint shows some gaps in Federation Services that could fully support users in successfully accessing and analyzing data over multiple TREs. This includes a central access point for user training, data discovery (including federated querying), data access application to multiple TREs, managing contractual agreements with multiple parties and Statistical Disclosure Control on the federation level. This central access should be supported by unified processes and federation-level governance. The gaps in the first version of the Blueprint presented in the current report will inform the next version of the Blueprint and thus contribute to a user-driven Blueprint definition.

In addition to gaps, the gap analysis has highlighted several additional requirements spanning across discovery services, AAAI, user training, software services, and disclosure control. These requirements, while not extending the Blueprint architecture, might inform the definition of individual Blueprint components, the AAAI system and the operating procedures that will be addressed in later versions of the ENTRUST Blueprint. In addition to the architectural components, this report thus provides a user perspective on how a federation of TREs should operate to maximally benefit the users.

The gap analysis presented in the present report did not directly assess gaps between the ENTRUST Blueprint and the existing EOSC infrastructure as well as other data spaces, such as EHDS. However, possible points for alignment with EOSC and EHDS were outlined in the discussion. Aligning the ENTRUST Blueprint with these data spaces will both foster interoperability between data spaces on the larger scale and help solve interoperability challenges that the Drivers face on the smaller scale.

7. Next steps

We aim to present and discuss the recommendations towards the ENTRUST Blueprint at the Requirements and Capabilities workshop planned by the Architecture WP for May 2025. In addition, we aim to discuss the AAAI requirements laid down in this report with WP16 (soon 17) to further inform the AAAI architecture. Within the WP itself (now WP7, soon to be labeled WP8) we will continue to streamline our requirements. Several Drivers plan to reach out to their stakeholder community through a survey to get a more in-depth understanding of the requirements from different perspectives, in particular covering the requirements from the angle of 1) the data holders, 2) the data users, and 3) the TRE providers. The separation between these perspectives is often not entirely clear since one party may have multiple roles (e.g. both data holder and TRE provider, or both data holder and data user). We will take particular care to ensure the requirements are provided from the perspective of a well-defined role.

Another challenge is to harmonize the requirements across the Drivers as much as possible. This is required to allow for the further processing of the requirements into the Blueprint; it would be very helpful if we could merge similar or even identical requirements across the Drivers. That is quite a laborious task; we aim to organise “show & tell” sessions between the Drivers where one Driver will be in the lead outlining their requirements and the other Drivers will try to merge their requirements as much as possible onto the presented requirements.

Finally, we also aim to implement prototypic installations of a TRE for each of the Drivers in order to create a tangible demonstrator for the requirements gathered.

Appendix 1: Gap analysis summary table

The table below lists the steps from the generic user journey in the first column (color coded per role: orange: data user/researcher; blue: TRE; green: data provider/controller). Driver requirements have been allocated to the user journey steps and the mapping from the ENTRUST Blueprint (Table 5.3.1 Mapping of key Driver requirements to the DARE UK Blueprint) has been incorporated.

User journey step	Requirement	Blueprint Capability	Gap	Driver
1. Discover data	Findability (R011)	Discovery Service	Should be in a unified service portal	3
	Metadata (R012, R022)	Discovery Service	Does the discovery happen inside or outside of the TRE? This can make a difference for highly sensitive data	4
	(Meta-)data quality checks/ standards (R023)	Discovery Service	- Minimal Information about a Dataset - Dataset quality label (e.g. quantum)	3
	Data Sharing Policy (R018)	Discovery Service	Data Sharing Policy should be accessible in Discovery Service	4
	Data (cohort) discovery (R030)	Job Submission Service	Should be in a unified service portal	1,3
2. Register at TRE	D16.1 Account Creation (R13); Identity Assurance (R14); Identity Freshness (R15)	AAAI	<i>No gaps:</i> we're assuming a central registration system in a unified service portal.	1, 3
			- Authenticating non-European users who don't have eIDAS - Some national regulations still don't support eID (or there are restrictions from which countries within EU are trusted)	4
			- Ideally, having the ability to record training would be included - i.e. like a type of 'R researcher Passport'. - The AAAI would need to talk to multiple training systems possibly, and would need to be queryable.	2
			GAP: Registration is currently possible at individual TREs only. Registering at one TRE should register you with the whole federation.	2
3. Complete data access	Data access requests (user)	not included	Assume standardised way to request access across resources / TREs	1

request	journey)		Should be funneled through a single point. E.g. Researcher only goes to one TRE, or another body, and they make the further requests on behalf of the researcher/ project.	3
4. Check and relay data request	Data access requests (user journey)	not included	Might have to be collected and submitted by the researcher.	2
5. Evaluate data access request	Data access requests (user journey)	not included	Needs a minimum set of standards for security/encryption.	2
			GAP: Approval process is missing from the Blueprint - this varies across TREs, some use data access committees, others don't. [note: national legislation might set different requirements for different datasets.]	2
6. Pass safe researcher training	Safe User training and certification (R014, R027) → D16.1 Entitlements (R12)	Federation services: Train user AAAI: Certify user	Not yet available at all TREs and is not included in the Blueprint at present. But it would be important to include, as this is one of the 5 Safes which are a base of a TRE. Further, this type of training is currently being developed at TREs that don't have it yet/ are planning to provide remote access to their secure access data.	2
			Should address the issue and awareness of data transfer to a 3rd country.	3
7. Sign data use agreement and TRE Service Agreement	Data Sharing/Transfer Agreement (R002)	not included	No such agreement template exists in UKDS or GESIS, in fact is not an option at the moment.	2
			- May require multiple agreements between multiple partners: Agreement registry (is this different to the Project Registry?) - Should be in a unified service portal	3
			Between company and university (but this needs to be checked)	4
8. Prepare project space	Backup (R034)	SDZ, RAZ, SDA	<i>No gaps</i>	
9. Install software	Software applications (R037)	Software Service	- Additional software can be added, if needed, depending on approval and validity checks. UKDS/GESIS users are not allowed to upload or install software themselves. - Access to the central repository for software packages within the federation. - Also 'Reference Drive' that users can access - common documentation and approved open source boundary data, etc.? - Can we agree on a list of common software/packages for federation? - Checking process for packages requested by	2

			users that are not on list (labour intensive).	
10. Pseudonymize data	Pseudonymization (user journey)	Index Service: Pseudonymization	- AAI but only the part for the user, not the project - Pseudonymisation is not correct here, it is too narrow - factually anonymised (GESIS) or de-identified (UKDS) is more accurate.	2
	Anonymization guidelines (R003)		Checks to ensure own/external data import request is included in project application	2
11. Make data accessible by project space	Encrypted data transfer (R001)	Security Server	Is often done way earlier in the process.	2
12. Give data user access to project space	2-factor authentication for TRE users (R024)	AAAI	<i>No gaps</i>	
13. Login	2-factor authentication for TRE users → D16.1 MFA (R9)	AAAI: authentication	AAAI should provide 2-factor authentication	3
			- There could be specific criteria for the authentication methods, such as biometrics etc. How to check the “freshness” of the identity information	4
14. Self-install pre-approved software	Internet connection from within TRE (R006)	Software Service	Self-installation is not allowed at GESIS or UKDS TRE or ODISSEI, it is done by TRE staff.	2
			- Alien software would need to be checked by TRE before installation - Internet connection from TRE should be discussed among providers, what are the risk scenarios? - Syncing repositories to TRE is more important than allowing PI's to upload software via the internet?	4
15. Import pre-approved data	Encrypted data transfer (R001)	Security Server	- Often not allowed by the data provider - User cannot import data themselves - needs to be done by TRE, seeking permission from all data owners of the data used in the project.	2
			Access to other genomic databases: Could be resolved by pre-downloaded additional datasets? Usually known in advance but not always (e.g. developing pipeline, finding a problem). Or follow data ingress process. Or allow access to limited external resources.	1
			To multiple TREs	3
	Data encryption at rest (R008)	Secure Data Zone	Should it be mandatory? Or other control measures can compensate for data encryption at rest (eg. Project's storage isolation)?	3

16. Analyse data	Data access and analysis (BP)	RAZ, QMZ	Not a linear process; perhaps more data & software is needed for which users much request approval from TRE/data owner	2
			Relates to step 9.: researchers have specific software needs, if TRE can't meet them, it's a gap	4
	Data standards (R019)	not included	Proprietary data standards, FAIR (as semantic interoperability) cannot be mandated, but can be strongly recommended (especially for interoperability reasons, so datasets can be enriched from other sources later) > GAP: training and communication about FAIR data for company representatives	4
17. Request export	Handling output requests (BP)	Output Control	Request output release (UKDS/GESIS), no data exported, only analytical outputs which are SDC checked	2
			Data controller needs to make the decision	4
18. Check and relay export request		Output Control	- Ongoing user support must be available during the duration of the project. - Automation of common requests would be desirable.	2
19. Evaluate export request	Handling output requests (BP), Output release (R013)	Output Control	Covered by the role of information governor	1
			- Need agreed definitions of terminology. Data provider needs to make the decision. RDC collecting their own data and making it available may have different opinions to archive. - Focus here is on personal data, but there are other reasons it may be sensitive - IPR, commercial, military, potential for harm, etc.	2
20. Export results	Retrieving output from TRE (R032)	Output Control	SDC checked and approved outputs only released (exported) at GESIS/UKDS	2
			- Where does the data go upon export? - Disclosure control? Checking that results do not disclose sensitive information	4
21. Publish	Data publishing (FAIR)	not included	Output references reported back to TRE after journal publication etc.	2
			Archiving capabilities?	3
			FAIR doesn't mandate publishing	4
	Data citation / credit attribution (R010, R029)	not included	How do we identify citations if only log files are checked and/or no DOI is allocated?	2
22. Close project space	Timely data deletion (R031)	Project environment	Requests for output release at (UKDS and /GESIS), no data is 'exported'.	2

	Archiving/ publication of data and code for future validation (R009, R026)	Software Service, SDZ	Use 'archive' instead of 'Close' (see below), so it can be reinstated if needed (e.g. following a peer review resulting in further requests). A clear archival policy should be in place and users should be made aware of it. (UKDS/GESIS retain project materials for 10 years).	2
general	Scalable infrastructure (R007)	Blueprint itself	<i>No gaps</i>	1
			- e.g. SafePod Network in the UK works and is well accepted by data owners. - Could be a stepping stone towards a Federation, if it is difficult to get data owners to agree to international federated access. May enable them to consent more easily until they can agree to full federation	2
	Compliance with varied legal frameworks (R016)	Federation services: registry of national and regional legislations and regulations (future extension)	Needs to be restricted to areas covered by GDPR or those countries where data protection legislation is felt to be compatible (decision of adequacy).	2
	Auditing process (R004)	AAAI	Company might want to appoint a representative to monitor the project and revoke rights if they find it necessary	4
	Certification (R028)	AAAI	<i>No gaps</i>	
	Usability (R038)		- Ongoing user support must be available during the project (sometimes difficult to separate user support in the TRE section from that done by the data holder) - Automation of common support requests desirable	2

Appendix 2: Driver requirements table

The table below lists the refined version of the Driver requirements as gathered for the M7.1 milestone report and is a snapshot of the working version of the Drivers' requirements, which is under constant revision through discussions within and between the Drivers and with other WPs. Five iterations of the requirements will be published throughout the EOSC-ENTRUST project, with the third iteration, an updated and harmonized list of requirements, included in the M8.1 milestone report planned for August 2025.

No.	Title	Description	Author	MoSCoW				SATRE Capability
				D1	D2	D3	D4	
R001	Data Encryption in transit	All data within the Trusted Research Environment must be encrypted in transit. This requirement aims to ensure that data is protected from unauthorized access or breaches.	D1	M	M	M	M	Information security
R002	Data Sharing Agreement	Establish a formal data-sharing agreement among participating institutions. This agreement should outline the terms and conditions for sharing data, including licensing, access controls, and data use limitations.	D1	S	M	M	S	Legal services
R003	Anonymization Agreement	Establish anonymization guidelines among participating institutions. This agreement should outline the set of techniques - and their use-cases - that best assure the privacy of the patient is respected	D1	S	S	S	C	Data lifecycle management
R004	Auditing process	Establish a set of verifiable - auditable - key characteristics among participating institutions. This requirement aims to ensure the limits of the word 'Trusted' in practice	D1	M	C	C	S	Quality Management
R005	Technology agreement	The current landscape of available TREs makes it quite difficult - if not directly impossible - to provide a single, comprehensive list of possible hardware or technologies to use.	D1	W	W	W	C	not included
R006	Internet connection from within TRE	Most of the genomic analyses require some kind of data on the outside	D1	S	W		S	not included

		world, be it a reference genome or annotation databases. In some cases these can be downloaded pre-analysis to the TRE, but this tends to hinder analysis workflows that, from the POV of the users, work on the outside of a TRE.						
R007	Scalable infrastructure	<i>[Red:] from M7/Blueprint, description and MoSCoW to be added</i>	D1					
R008	Data Encryption at rest	All data within the Trusted Research Environment must be encrypted at rest. This requirement aims to ensure that data is protected from unauthorized access or breaches.	D1	M	S	C	C	Information security
R009	Archiving of syntax for future validation or reproducibility	Syntax/code to be archived indefinitely for future validation/reproducibility purposes (peer review)	D2		M		C	Output management
R010	Data citation	Data to be cited (including doi) in outputs	D2	C	M		C	not included
R011	Findability	Central Portal for research data discovery (improved CESSDA portal?, New portal, harvesting info of existing ones?)	D2	C	S	S	C	Information search and discovery
R012	Metadata	Metadata available in one language (English)	D2	S	S		S	Research Meta-Data
R013	Output release	Output release following SDC checks performed by the TRE, should have clear SDC rules that are consistent with recognised best practice	D2	C	M	M	M	Output management
R014	Safe Researcher' training and/or passport	Training on using the TRE project space, statistical disclosure & data access. The possible inclusion of electronic training records to be explored.	D2	S	M		S	Member Accreditation
R015	Data transfer between environments		D2		C		C	not included
R016	Compliance with various national legal frameworks for data sharing	<i>[Red:] from M7/Blueprint, description and MoSCoW to be added</i>	D2					
R018	Data Sharing Policy	A Data Sharing Policy / Data Access Policy is a common element needed for TREs operating with clinical trial data.	D3	C	M	S	C	Legal services
R019	Data standards	Implementing a data standards conversion service is a feature that TREs dedicated to clinical trials offer (e.g. IDDO, Clinical Study Data Request). In clinical trials the most frequently used data standards	D3	C	na	S	S	not included

		suite is CDISC. For routinely collected healthcare data OMOP is a data standard that is gaining momentum in the EU. Mapping services across OMOP-CDISC would be useful for healthcare data to be used in regulatory submissions. Especially the FDA (USA), the PMDA (Japan) mandate the use of CDISC for application and the NMPA (China) recommends. No such requirement from the EMA yet.						
R020	Data Transfer Agreement	A TRE that wants to cover datasets from a specific data type needs to provide to potential data providers a Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) template that covers necessary requirements specific to the data type. DTAs at least per data type should be standardised but some flexibility should be provided to cover the different legal obligations of the data controllers (data providers).	D3	M	C	M	S	Legal services
R021	Data Use Agreement	A TRE that wants to cover datasets from a specific data type needs to provide a model Data Use Agreement (DUA) that covers necessary requirements specific to the data type. DUAs should include access prerequisites, requirements and obligations.	D3	C	M	M	M	Legal services
R022	Metadata	For clinical trials, all data objects within a Trusted Research Environment must have detailed metadata describing both the clinical study that generated them and each data object individually. Metadata should cover as a minimum discovery, access and provenance.	D3		S	S	S	Meta-Data Search and Discovery Application
R023	(Meta-)data quality checks/standards	Could implement a data quality framework to be recommended to data providers. Must have metadata quality checks. Clinical trial data is already of good quality due to rigorous processes, regulations, audits that come with the conduct of a trial. A data quality label could be useful for data coming from healthcare if we want them to be used in clinical trials for regulatory submissions.	D3	C	C	C	C	Quality Management
R024	2-factor authentication for TRE users	2-factor authentication is a critical security measure in TREs to ensure that only authorized individuals can access sensitive data. E.g. username and password + OTP.	D3	C	M	M	C	Identity and access management

R025	Archiving of datasets for future validation or reproducibility under regulations.	Some datasets, notably in the clinical trials area, must be preserved long-term for regulatory reasons. This may also be coupled with a particular analysis environment (code, scripts, intermediate results etc.) (see below). The dataset will need to be archived securely, which introduces the possible need for formal digital archiving processes, curation actions etc. TREs supporting clinical trials must have this capability.	D3	C	S	M	C	Data Archiving
R026	Archiving of study analysis environments (code, intermediate results, etc.) for future validation or reproducibility under regulations.	covered in R009, to be harmonized	D3	C	S	S	C	Study Management
R027	Basic training on the use the TRE's project space	Potential users are not necessarily familiar with working in a TRE. Basic user guidelines or guidance videos or ad-hoc training could be an option to increase user friendliness and user satisfaction.	D3	S	M	C	S	Knowledge management
R028	Certification	Demonstrate good information management and security via certifications: e.g., ISO/IEC 27001 - Information Security Management, ISO/IEC 27701 -Privacy Information Management	D3	S	S	S	S	Information security
R029	Credit attribution to the original data generator	Often publications coming out by research provided by others require a review process by the original data provider's team. Often also credit attribution is required (e.g., co-authorship / acknowledgement in publications)	D3	C	S	C	C	Knowledge management
R030	Data (Cohort) Discovery	A, perhaps automated, process for identifying suitable data for a research project or clinical trial. Might be federated to allow for multi-TRE querying (See HDR Cohort Discovery Tool)	D3	C	S	C	S	Meta-Data Search and Discovery Application
R031	Data kept only within the agreed time period	Mechanisms for timely deletion of the data (e.g., from users' project space when this exceeds the authorised period or completely from the TRE when this goes beyond the data provider's requirements).	D3	S	S	M	C	Data Archiving
R032	Retrieving output from TRE	End-user needs to have the possibility to retrieve the output of their analyses from TRE.	D3	C	W	M	M	Output management

R033	Accessibility of TRE's services and administrative processes (previously service design)	It is necessary to create easy access to services of the TRE for end-users in different roles. The services should be designed to support easy processes to share and analyse data. User-centred design practices would help archiving this requirement. They might also be a requirement in their own right.	D4		S	C	S	End user computing
R034	Backup	TRE should create a backup copy of the data analyses for the full length of the research project.	D4	S	M	S	S	Information security
R035	Details of TRE operations, data available and projects which have accessed the data should NOT be required to be publicly available.	This requirement is a justification to an already existing requirement in SATRE. However, the existing requirement is not always applicable for private-public partnership. The existing version goes: Details of TRE operations, data available and projects which have accessed the data should be publicly available (*optional for TREs without personal data).	D4				S	Public Involvement and Engagement
R036	Ethical guidance	TRE should assure that users understand their ethical responsibilities while analysing sensitive data. The guidance could be offered by the TRE. It is also possible for the TRE to require organisations that use their services to offer such guidance for the users from their organisation.	D4	C	M		S	Data lifecycle management
R037	Software applications	End-users should be able to use appropriate and familiar software applications for data analysis.	D4	S	M	M	S	End user computing
R038	Usability	User interface's ease of use is of most importance for end-users that represent private organizations. Private organizations are used to commercial services with good usability. In addition they usually have the possibility to choose between private service providers and TREs.	D4	C	S	S	M	End user computing